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BUILDING CLIMATIC PROPERTIES OF LIGHTWEIGHT FACADES

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Lightweight constructions are assumed to not have the same performance as massive constructions regarding building physics and climate. Experimental studies show however that lightweight building envelopes made out of textile-reinforced concrete are hygrothermal at least equal to conventional envelopes. Thus, it was proven that lightweight constructions have good properties concerning indoor and surface climate as well as durability. In addition, textile-reinforced concrete contributes to sustainable building, such as reducing the needed amount of cement and sand. In this study, a facade of textile-reinforced concrete was developed that surpasses or at least is equal to most building physical properties of conventional constructions. Furthermore, selected requirements for building physics and architecture (e.g., thermal energy storage over the day) were examined and compared to conventional constructions. The main results are: It has been found that lightweight constructions made of textile concrete exceed the contribution to summer thermal protection in most cases compared to conventional building constructions. These results will form the basis for future ways of building facades. They will be much lighter and thus architecturally more appealing without adversely affecting the buildings' physical and climatic properties.

Keywords: building physics, indoor climatic properties, textile-reinforced concrete, facade elements, sustainable building

1 INTRODUCTION

The European Green Deal defines the goal of Europe being the first climate-neutral continent by 2050. The European Climate Act establishes the EU's voluntary commitment and the first milestone for reaching this goal. The greenhouse gas emissions should be reduced by at least 55 % until 2030 compared to 1990. Since then, greenhouse gas emissions have already decreased by 24 % while the economy has grown by 60 %. (European Climate Law, 2021)

The building sector is responsible for 36 % of all greenhouse gas emissions in the EU (European Court of Auditors, 2020). This makes it an important key in achieving the set goals in the European Climate Change Act. Buildings should be notably more efficient throughout their life cycle in terms of production, operation and deconstruction. In Germany, these requirements are implemented by the GEG (Gebäudeenergiegesetz, 2020).

However, this leads to thicker building constructions using classic building materials for facade. The solution are innovative composite materials such as textile-reinforced concrete in combination with highly efficient insulating materials such as aerogels.

While the requirements on the facade are continuously increasing, the environmental impact and costs are supposed to decrease a contradiction that can only be solved by innovative materials.

Buildings made of textile-reinforced concrete promise not only to reduce manufacturing energy, but also operating energy with intelligent planning (Kahnt, 2021).

2 INITIAL SITUATION

The demand for cooling energy will rise furthermore in the coming years. When cooling is required in the building, additional components regarding the building technology have to be installed. This is included in the manufacturing energy (gray energy), but causes also a significant increase of the operating energy, when the building is in use. In the Central European climate the fluctuations of the outside temperatures can be used to significantly reduce the hours of excess temperature and thus completely eliminate the need for cooling.

For a comparison, a west-facing office room was simulated as a group office according to DIN V 18599-10:2016-10 with a size of 22 m² in the reference climate of Potsdam, Germany. The facade area was 12 m² with a window area of 6 m². Only an interior sunshade shielded the room from sunlight. The three interior wall surfaces were defined as adiabatic in contrast to the facade. All wall surfaces (43 m²) had the same wall structure including insulation layer. The achieved temperatures and the demanded cooling energy form the basis for the evaluation. A detailed description of the study can be found in Kahnt (2021).

Figure 1. Comparison of the room air temperatures in the group office, air-conditioned and non-air-conditioned

Figure 1 shows the temperatures in the office over four days in a period prone to overheating. The three working days (Wednesday, 15.8. to Friday, 17.8.) are highlighted in white during the time of use from 7 a.m. to 6 p.m. At the other times, the office is unused (gray). At night or on the weekend (Saturday, 18.8.) the night ventilation is turned on in the air-conditioned and non-air-conditioned version. In the air-conditioned version, additional cooling is provided during the time of use. The outdoor air temperatures are significantly higher than the room temperatures on the first few days. However, they drop significantly at night so that the cold outside air can be used. Without air conditioning, an indoor air temperature of 30 °C is reached on Thursday, 16.8. When the room is

cooled (version "air-conditioned"), the indoor air temperature is steady at 26 °C during the time of use.

However, this necessary cooling energy for the office can also be compensated by increasing the thermal energy storage of building constructions over the day together with a double night ventilation as examined in this study.

Three different building constructions were selected (see Figure 2 to Figure 4): an old building wall with a thermal resistance of 0,66 m²·K/W, a wooden and a textile-reinforced concrete wall with each a thermal resistance of 4,55 m²·K/W. These wall constructions are applied for both the facade and the interior walls of the simulated office.

Figure 2. Old building wall, load-bearing

Figure 3. Wooden wall, load-bearing

Figure 4. Textile-reinforced concrete wall, non-load-bearing

3 SOLUTION APPROACHES

For all three building constructions, the heat flow was evaluated. The non-air-conditioned indoor air temperature was set as a boundary condition for the simulation. The cooling energy from the reference construction was distributed to the 43 m² interior wall surfaces. Thus, it could be examined whether the building construction had a similar performance as the cooling. From the results, a general qualitative statement for the indoor climate was derived.

Figure 5. Thermal energy storage of the old building wall

Figure 5 shows the heat flows of the uninsulated old building wall over the surface. The positive values describe the heat flow into the building construction and the negative the heat flow out of the it. During the hours of use (7 a.m. to 6 p.m.), the office space has high internal and external heat loads. These need to be absorbed during the time of use and released again at night via night ventilation. The boundary line of the blue area describes the heat flow into or out of the building construction. The resulting blue area shows the total thermal energy storage. When the building construction is optimized for this use, it can absorb thermal energy at least up to the dashed line during the day and release it again at night. The dashed line describes the target heat flow from the reference construction including cooling energy.

The old building wall can absorb the high heat loads from the room. The dashed line is often reached or exceeded. This means that the indoor climate can be kept mostly at a comfortable level. At night and on weekends, the temporarily stored thermal energy can be released again. (Kahnt, 2021)

Figure 6. Thermal energy storage of the wooden wall

Figure 6 shows the heat flows of the wooden wall over the surface. The inner 8.8 cm of the wood cladding do not achieve the desired thermal energy storage, because the 2 cm thick laminated spruce board participates mostly in the storage. The layer of air behind it largely separates the board from this process. In addition, the material spruce is ill-suited for thermal energy storage in the daily cycle because of its low thermal conductivity and density. The same applies to plaster-board.

The dashed line is not reached, because the wooden wall can not absorb the high heat loads on the simulated days. Thus, there are hours of excess temperature outside the comfortable level according to DIN EN ISO 7730:2006-05. (Kahnt, 2021)

Figure 7. Thermal energy storage of the textile-reinforced wall

The best results of the study achieve the textile concrete wall with a ribbed construction (see Figure 7). The actual thermal energy storage of this building construction was able to exceed the required storage during the time of use. Textile-reinforced concrete has a high density, a good but not yet ideal thermal conductivity and a high specific heat storage capacity. These three properties define the thermal effusivity, which describes the ability to absorb thermal energy over a period of time. The result was further enhanced by slots (cooling ribs). It increased the surface for the penetrating thermal energy to increase the amount of absorbed thermal energy. Ribs are generally recommended for building materials with low thermal conductivities such as wood or plasterboard. However, the textile-reinforced concrete would have achieved equally good properties even without the ribs, but the thermal conductivity of the concrete matrix has to be increased further.

The dashed line was exceeded most of the time. This means that the internal and external heat loads are absorbed by the textile-reinforced concrete wall during the time of use. In addition, the thermal energy is completely released by the night ventilation in the following night. (Kahnt, 2021)

4 RESULTS

In this study, the performance of lightweight textile-reinforced concrete facades was compared to a solid wall of an old building and shows that lightweight walls can have a good thermal energy storage like solid building constructions. Thus, lightweight walls can not only save raw materials in the production phase of a building due to the slimmer constructions, but reduces also the necessary operating energy significantly during use. Therefore, it is an ideal basis for sustainable nearly zero-energy buildings.

References

- DIN EN ISO 7730:2006-05, *Ergonomics of the thermal environment – Analytical determination and interpretation of thermal comfort using calculation of the PMV and PPD indices and local thermal comfort criteria*, Beuth, Berlin, 2006.
- DIN V 18599-10:2016-10, *Energy efficiency of buildings – Calculation of the net, final and primary energy demand for heating, cooling, ventilation, domestic hot water and lighting – Part 10: Boundary conditions of use, climatic data*, Beuth, Berlin, 2016.
- European Climate Law, Official Journal of the European Union, 2021.
- European Court of Auditors, *Energy efficiency in buildings: greater focus on cost-effectiveness still needed. Special Report, Nr. 11, 2020*: Publications Office. <https://doi.org/10.2865/86720>, 2020.
- Gebäudeenergiegesetz, Bonn, 2020.
- Kahnt, A., *The building envelope of the future – Development of a textile reinforced-concrete facade* (Thesis), TU Dresden, Retrieved from <https://www.baufachinformation.de/die-gebaeudehuelle-der-zukunft-entwicklung-einer-textilbetonfassade-vom-baustoff-bis-zum-raumklima/buecher/254703>, Dresden, 2021.